

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Patient Education and Counseling

journal homepage: www.journals.elsevier.com/patient-education-and-counseling

Awareness about the risk of hearing loss after ototoxic treatments in Swiss childhood cancer survivors

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: The International Guideline Harmonization Group recommends childhood cancer survivors (CCS) exposed to ototoxic treatments be aware of the risk of hearing loss. We assessed awareness among adult CCS.

Methods: We identified adults diagnosed with cancer < 20 years who received ototoxic treatments through the Swiss Childhood Cancer Registry (ChCR) and invited them to the HEAR-study. Participants completed a questionnaire and underwent pure-tone audiometry. Cancer and treatment data were obtained from the ChCR. We used logistic regression to explore factors influencing awareness.

Results: Of 424 invited, 105 CCS participated (25 %). Fifty-seven percent did not remember receiving information on hearing loss prior to the study. CCS who remembered being informed were more likely diagnosed after 1995 (OR: 4.5, 95 % CI: 1.3–15.4), reported hearing problems (10.9, 2.6–45.1) and other late effects (4.1, 1.3–13.2), and treated with platinum chemotherapy only (10.8, 2.2–53.2) versus cranial radiotherapy only. 44 % of participants presented clinically relevant hearing loss.

Conclusions: Over half of CCS exposed to ototoxic treatments were unaware of their risk of hearing loss.

Practice Implications: Educating CCS about potential late effects of ototoxic treatments is important to allow early diagnosis and treatment, especially for those who had cancer longer ago and those exposed to cranial radiation.

1. Introduction

Childhood cancer survivors (CCS) are at risk of hearing loss as a late effect of certain treatments [1]. Forty percent of CCS treated with platinum chemotherapy, around 20 % of those treated with doses of cranial radiation ≥ 30 gray (Gy), and varying proportions of those treated with surgery involving the auditory system experience hearing loss [1–6]. Cumulative incidence of hearing loss due to these treatments increases up to 15 years after completing cancer treatment [7]. Among CCS, undetected hearing loss can impair language development, school performance, neurocognitive functions, and overall quality of life [8–11]. Regular audiometric screening enables hearing loss to be detected as early as possible and allows appropriate measures to be initiated. The International Guideline Harmonization Group (IGHG) recommends that CCS treated with a known ototoxic treatment

(cisplatin with or without high-dose carboplatin (> 1500 mg/m²), and/or head or brain radiotherapy ≥ 30 Gy) and their health-care providers “should be aware of the risk of hearing loss” [1]. IGHG recommends annual hearing tests until six years of age, biannual tests until twelve years, and every five years thereafter [1].

Informing CCS about the risk for late effects related to their cancer treatment is important to facilitate follow-up care and to manage long-term health [12,13]. Previous research in Switzerland suggests CCS have limited knowledge about their risks for late effects [14–16]. Studies investigating information provision on specific late effects, such as hearing loss, are lacking.

Using data from the HEAR-study, a health service research project on the hearing of CCS, we first examined whether adult CCS who had received ototoxic treatments were aware of their risk for hearing loss, and had their hearing evaluated as recommended. Second, we compared

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2025.108764>

Received 25 September 2024; Received in revised form 21 February 2025; Accepted 20 March 2025

Available online 27 March 2025

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CCS who were aware of hearing loss risk with those who were not to identify CCS at increased need for information and support. Third, we investigated whether CCS currently experience clinically relevant hearing loss and explored the associations between awareness, hearing evaluation after end of treatment, and current hearing loss based on audiometric testing.

2. Methods

2.1. Study population

We identified eligible CCS through the Swiss Childhood Cancer Registry (ChCR), which is a national registry that includes all Swiss residents since 1976 who were diagnosed before the age of 20 with leukemias, lymphomas, central nervous system (CNS) tumors, malignant solid tumors, or Langerhans cell histiocytosis [17,18]. For this study, we included CCS registered in the ChCR who survived at least two years since diagnosis, received ototoxic treatment as defined per IGHG guidelines, and were aged 18 years or older at the time of study. We included only adults in this project because in the Swiss healthcare system, pediatric survivors typically receive all required follow-up examinations centralized in pediatric follow-up, which includes hearing tests. When they turn 18 years, they transition into adult follow-up care, which is often not centralized. After this transition, many survivors are lost to follow-up [19–21], which may lead to reduced awareness and monitoring of late effects. We excluded CCS who lacked a valid address, were living outside Switzerland, did not speak German or French, and had been contacted for another study in the past six months (January 2022–July 2022). The Ethics Committee of the Canton of Bern approved the ChCR (166/2014) and the HEAR-study (2021–01624).

2.2. Procedures and study design

The HEAR-study is a health service research project set up in 2021 at the University of Bern, Switzerland. Details have been published previously [22]. Eligible CCS were invited by postal mail; we sent up to two reminders to CCS who did not respond. CCS who responded with informed consent received an e-mail request to complete an online questionnaire (Supplementary Table S1) and an invitation to attend a free hearing test. We asked participants to fill in the questionnaire before scheduling a hearing test at a local hearing aid shop where a certified acoustician performed bilateral pure-tone audiometry (125–8000 Hz) with an additional bone conduction measurement (250–4000 Hz) if the hearing threshold was > 25 dB. We collected questionnaires and audiograms between July 15, 2022, and July 15, 2023.

2.3. Hearing-related information

2.3.1. Awareness about the risk of hearing loss and information on prior hearing evaluations

We assessed awareness about the risk of hearing loss using a questionnaire. We asked participants if they had been informed about an increased risk of hearing loss (yes/no/don't know). We also asked if they had been counseled to monitor their hearing after end of treatment (yes/no/don't know). If participants answered yes to either of the two questions, we coded being informed as "yes". Further, we asked if their hearing had ever been evaluated after end of treatment (yes/no/don't know).

2.3.2. Self-reported hearing loss, perceived hearing difficulties, and other late effects

We asked participants if they experienced any late effects of cancer or its therapy (yes/no), and to list them. We created a variable "late effects other than hearing loss" (yes/no) for which "yes" indicated participants who reported any late effect other than hearing loss, including both psychological (e.g. depression, fatigue) and somatic (e.g.

pulmonary, cardiac). If participants listed hearing loss as a late effect in the open question, the variable on self-reported hearing loss was coded as "yes". Further, we asked if they had problems following a conversation when there was background noise (hearing difficulties in noisy environments) (yes/no) and if they felt they did not hear well (feeling of poor hearing) (yes, often/yes, sometimes/no).

2.3.3. Hearing loss from audiogram measurements

The hearing aid shops sent us audiogram results in a coded file. For grading we visualized the audiograms using the R package "audiometry" (Lehnert B, R package version 0.3.0, 2021) in RStudio (R Core Team, Vienna, AUT, 2022). Two trained researchers (PJ and CN) independently graded audiograms for each ear according to the SIOP Boston Ototoxicity Scale [23], an established grading scheme used for CCS exposed to ototoxic treatments [24,25]. We resolved discrepancies through discussions with an experienced audiologist (MK). We considered bone conduction measurements when there was consistently a significant difference between air and bone conduction measurements (≥ 10 dB), indicating a potential conductive hearing loss [23]. We used the grading of the more affected ear. Severity was graded as (a) none (grade 0), (b) mild (grade 1), (c) moderate (grade 2), or (d) severe hearing loss (\geq grade 3) [23]. Clinically relevant hearing loss was defined as SIOP Boston grade ≥ 2 [23,25].

2.4. Participant characteristics

2.4.1. Clinical and cancer-treatment related characteristics

The ChCR provided data on biological sex, year of birth, cancer diagnosis, age at diagnosis, year of diagnosis, and type of therapy, including carboplatin chemotherapy, cisplatin chemotherapy, and cranial radiation. We compared participants to nonparticipants based on these characteristics provided by the ChCR.

2.4.2. Information on follow-up care

We asked participants in the questionnaire if they were still undergoing clinical follow-up care related to their cancer (yes/no), and if they had received any information regarding follow-up care in general (yes/no/don't know).

2.4.3. Socioeconomic characteristics

The questionnaire assessed sociodemographic characteristics including migration background (yes/no), participants' and their parents' education levels, and language region (German/French). Participants were categorized as having a migration background if at least one parent was born outside Switzerland. We defined three education level categories: primary schooling (compulsory schooling only, ≤ 9 years), secondary education (vocational training, upper secondary education), and tertiary education (university, or technical college).

2.5. Statistical analysis

First, we assessed how many CCS were aware of a risk of hearing problems (information status) and how many had completed a hearing evaluation after the end of treatment. For further analysis, we combined the categories "no" and "don't know" interpreting both as insufficient awareness. Next, we assessed severity of hearing loss and prevalence of clinically relevant hearing loss (SIOP Boston Grade ≥ 2). Using univariable logistic regression, we investigated factors associated with information status and having completed a hearing evaluation after end of treatment (Supplementary Tables S2 and S3). We included sex, age at study, time since diagnosis, age at diagnosis, year of diagnosis, language region, participant and parental education, migration background, presence of late effects other than hearing loss, self-reported hearing loss, general information received on follow-up care, attending regular follow-up care visits, and treatment (only platinum/only cranial radiation ≥ 30 Gy/both platinum and cranial radiation) as explanatory

variables. We categorized year of diagnosis into the periods before and after 1995, reflecting a cut-off after which a decline in hearing loss was observed in previous studies of CCS from Switzerland [7]. Information status was included as an additional explanatory variable for the outcome hearing evaluation. In a multivariable logistic regression, we included all exposures associated with the outcome at a significance level of $p \leq 0.1$ [26]. If there were missing values in independent or dependent variables, we performed complete case analyses.

3. Results

3.1. Study population

Of 573 eligible CCS exposed to ototoxic treatments, identified through the ChCR, 424 were invited to the study. One-hundred and five (25 %) consented and completed the questionnaire and 83 (20 %) also completed a hearing test as part of our study (Supplementary Figure SF1). About half ($n = 57$, 54 %) of participants were female, median age at study start was 32 years (interquartile range [IQR]: 24–37), age at diagnosis 8 years (IQR: 4–13), and median time since diagnosis 23 years (IQR: 19–32) (Table 1). Common diagnoses were malignant bone tumors ($n = 24$, 23 %), CNS tumors ($n = 23$, 22 %) and soft tissue sarcomas ($n = 22$, 21 %). Eighty CCS (76 %) had been treated with platinum chemotherapy, and 41 (39 %) with cranial radiation (Supplementary Table S4). Compared to nonparticipants, CCS completing the questionnaire were more often female, older at time of study, further away from diagnosis and differed in type of cancer diagnosis (Supplementary

Table 1
Characteristics of participants completing the questionnaire (N = 105).

	Completed questionnaire N = 105 n (%); median (IQR/range)
Sex	
Female	57 (54)
Male	48 (46)
Age at study, years (median, IQR)	32 (24–37)
Year of diagnosis (median, range)	1998 (1977–2018)
1977–1995	41 (39)
1996–2005	46 (44)
2006–2018	18 (17)
Time since diagnosis, years (median, IQR)	23 (19–32)
Age at cancer diagnosis, years (median, IQR)	8 (4–13)
Diagnostic group of primary neoplasm (ICCC–3)	
Leukemias	0 (0)
Lymphomas	7 (7)
CNS tumors	23 (22)
Neuroblastoma	13 (12)
Retinoblastoma	3 (3)
Renal tumors	2 (2)
Hepatic tumors	4 (4)
Malignant bone tumors	24 (23)
Soft tissue sarcomas	22 (21)
Germ cell tumors	7 (7)
Other	0 (0)
Platinum Chemotherapy	
No platinum chemotherapy	23 (22)
Cisplatin	42 (40)
Carboplatin	17 (16)
Cisplatin & Carboplatin	21 (20)
Unknown	2 (2)
Cranial radiation	
No cranial radiation	64 (61)
< 30 Gray	0 (0)
≥ 30 Gray	41 (39)
Unknown	0 (0)
Education	
Primary schooling	5 (5)
Secondary education	57 (54)
Tertiary education	43 (41)

Abbreviations: IQR, Interquartile range. n, number. ICCC-3, international classification of childhood cancer, edition 3

Table S5).

3.2. Information status and prior hearing evaluation

Among 105 participants, 46 (44 %, 95 % confidence interval [CI]: 35–54 %) reported having received information or advice regarding risk of hearing loss or necessity of conducting hearing tests after end of treatment, while 31 (30 %, 95 % CI: 22–39 %) reported not having received information/advice and 28 (27 %, 95 % CI: 19–36 %) did not remember (Fig. 1). Similarly, 40 (38 %, 95 % CI: 29–48 %) participants reported having completed a hearing evaluation after end of treatment, 34 (32 %, 95 % CI: 24–42 %) reported not having completed a hearing evaluation, and 31 (30 %, 95 % CI: 22–39 %) did not remember. Of the 40 participants reporting a hearing evaluation, 13 (33 %) completed it in the last 5 years, 12 (30 %) completed it longer ago, and 15 (38 %) did not remember the year of their last hearing evaluation (Supplementary Table S6).

We visualized the relationship between information status and prior hearing evaluation using a proportional Venn diagram (Fig. 1). Most CCS who were informed also had their hearing evaluated at some point after treatment.

3.3. Degree of hearing loss and information status, self-reported hearing loss, and prior hearing evaluation

Of 83 participants who completed a hearing test for the study, 29 had normal hearing (35 %, 95 % CI: 25–46), 17 (20 %, 95 % CI: 13–31 %) had mild, 11 (13 %, 95 % CI: 7–23 %) moderate, and 26 (31 %, 95 % CI: 22–42 %) severe hearing loss, resulting in 37 participants (45 %, 95 % CI: 34–56 %) with clinically relevant hearing loss. One person with clinically relevant hearing loss did not complete the questionnaire. Among the 36 participants with clinically relevant hearing loss who completed the questionnaire, 20 (56 %, 95 % CI: 39–71 %) reported having received information/advice regarding their risk for hearing loss and 14 (39 %, 95 % CI: 24–56 %) reported having had their hearing evaluated after end of treatment. Further, 19 (53 %, 95 % CI: 36–69 %) of the participants with clinically relevant hearing loss reported prior hearing problems in the questionnaire, 29 (81 %, 95 % CI: 64–91 %) reported hearing difficulties in noisy environments, and 30 (83 %, 95 % CI: 67–93 %) sometimes or often felt like they were not hearing well. (Fig. 2)

3.4. Factors associated with information status and hearing evaluation after end of treatment

Participants informed about risk of hearing loss were diagnosed more often after 1995 (odds ratio [OR]: 4.5, 95 % CI: 1.3–15.4), reported more prior hearing problems (OR: 10.9, 95 % CI: 2.6–45.1) and other late effects (OR: 4.1, 95 % CI: 1.3–13.2), and were more often treated with platinum chemotherapy (OR: 10.8, 95 % CI: 2.2–53.2) or both platinum chemotherapy and cranial radiotherapy (OR: 6.5, 95 % CI: 1.0–41.8) compared to cranial radiotherapy alone (Table 2). Those who were informed were more likely to have had their hearing evaluated after end of treatment (OR: 13.6, 95 % CI: 3.8–48.3).

4. Discussion and conclusion

4.1. Summary of findings

This study found that over half of CCS who received ototoxic treatment reported they were unaware of the risk of hearing loss even though international guidelines recommend that they be aware. More than half did not remember having ever had their hearing evaluated after end of treatment. We found a strong association between being informed and having had a hearing evaluation. Almost half of participants had clinically relevant hearing loss assessed by pure-tone audiometry, yet almost

Fig. 1. Participant responses to questions on awareness and prior hearing evaluation. Participants who reported (a) having been informed or advised about the possibility of hearing loss and the need for hearing tests after completing therapy and (b) having had a hearing evaluation after completing the therapy. Proportional Venn-Diagram depicting the relation between having been informed or advised and having had a hearing evaluation. Numbers represent the number (n) and percentage (%) of participants reporting yes to the respective question; (a) Informed/Advised, Were you informed about hearing loss as a potential late effect of your treatment / Have you been advised to have your hearing checked after completing your therapies? (b) Hearing evaluated, Has your hearing ever been checked after you finished your treatment? No/Don't know; Answered no or do not know to both questions. Abbreviations: n, number.

Fig. 2. Degree of hearing loss assessed with audiograms and graded according to SIOP Boston ototoxicity scale, and responses of questions on awareness with clinically relevant hearing loss (Grade ≥ 2). (left) Degree of hearing loss according to SIOP Boston Ototoxicity Scale for participants with available audiograms, N = 83. No hearing loss, grade 0. Mild, grade 1. Moderate, grade 2. Severe, \geq grade 3. (right) Participants with clinically relevant hearing loss (SIOP Boston ototoxicity scale ≥ 2 , n = 36) who completed the baseline questionnaire and status on information/advice received on hearing loss (yes/no), hearing evaluated after therapy end (yes/no), self-reported hearing loss (yes/no), hearing difficulties in noisy environments (yes/no) and feeling of poor hearing (yes/no). 95 % Confidence intervals are displayed for those reporting “Yes”. ^a Participants with clinically relevant hearing loss who did not complete the baseline questionnaire were excluded from this graphic (n = 1). Abbreviations: SIOP, International Society of Paediatric Oncology. n, number.

half of those did not report hearing problems in the questionnaire, which suggests they were not aware of their hearing loss.

4.2. Information status

Previous surveys on information provision and information needs among Swiss CCS show that approximately one-third of survivors do not remember having ever received general information about potential late effects of their cancer or therapy, and about 80 % of CCS wish to be better informed [14–16]. In this study, 56 % of CCS did not remember receiving information about the risk for hearing loss. This is comparable to a Norwegian study about information provision in which up to 60 % of cancer survivors overall did not recall receiving information on late

effects including hearing loss, though the study also included survivors without ototoxic treatments [12]. A study from Hong Kong assessing knowledge about risk-based, exposure-related late effects found that, similar to our study, almost 60 % of CCS were not aware of potential hearing problems following ototoxic treatments [13].

4.2.1. Associations with information status

Consistent with other studies [12,14,15], we found that CCS seem to be less well informed the more time has passed since diagnosis. A reason for this might be that parents of patients who were younger children were the primary recipients of information [27]. Parents might not have passed on the information to their children, or CCS may have forgotten it given a long median time of 22 years since diagnosis.

Table 2

Factors associated with a) having received information/advice about hearing loss, and b) having ever completed a hearing evaluation after therapy; results from multivariable regressions.

Multivariable (95 %-CI)	Informed/Advised ^{a,b}		Hearing evaluated ^{a,b}	
	N = 102		N = 102	
	OR (95 %-CI)	p-value	OR (95 %-CI)	p-value
<i>Period of cancer diagnosis</i>				
≤ 1995	1.0		1.0	
> 1995	4.5	0.02	2.2	0.23
	(1.3–15.4)		(0.6–8.5)	
<i>Late effects other than hearing loss</i>				
No	1.0		1.0	
Yes	4.1	0.02	2.8	0.11
	(1.3–13.2)		(0.8–9.6)	
<i>Self-reported hearing loss</i>				
No	1.0		1.0	
Yes	10.9	< 0.01	0.7	0.59
	(2.6–45.1)		(0.2–2.7)	
<i>Maternal education</i>				
Primary or secondary education	1.0		1.0	
Tertiary education	1.7	0.38	1.6	0.43
	(0.5–5.5)		(0.5–5.3)	
<i>General information received on follow-up care</i>				
No	1.0		1.0	
Yes	1.1	0.87	1.3	0.65
	(0.4–3.3)		(0.4–4.4)	
<i>Information/advice received on hearing loss and hearing screening</i>				
No	‡		1.0	
Yes	‡		13.6	< 0.01
			(3.8–48.3)	
<i>Regular visit of follow-up care</i>				
No	1.0		1.0	
Yes	1.9	0.30	1.0	0.95
	(0.6–6.6)		(0.2–3.8)	
<i>Treatment group</i>				
Cranial radiation ≥ 30	1.0		1.0	
Gray only				
Platinum Chemotherapy only	10.8	< 0.01	1.8	0.49
	(2.2–53.2)		(0.3–9.4)	
Both	6.5	0.05	0.9	0.90
	(1.0–41.8)		(0.1–6.4)	

The respective multivariable model was adjusted for variables with a p-value of 0.1 or less in the univariable logistic regression.

‡, Exposure equal to outcome

Abbreviations: CI, Confidence Interval. OR, Odds Ratio. n, number.

^a People with missing maternal education and missing treatment group were excluded from the logistic regression (n = 3).

^b Age at study start and years since diagnosis were omitted from multivariable regression for collinearity with year of diagnosis.

We found that CCS diagnosed after 1995 were better informed, which is likely due to advances in knowledge about long-term effects of ototoxic treatments. For example, the American Speech-Language-Hearing Association (ASHA) guideline from 1994 recommended monitoring the hearing at least until one year post-treatment with platinum agents and only longer if hearing loss was detected [28]. Considering that one-third of our study population was diagnosed before 1995, they likely received outdated or limited information about potential long-term effects.

The 1994 ASHA guideline further stated that cranial radiation alone has little effect on hearing [28], and many clinicians might be less aware of the effect of cranial radiation on hearing than platinum chemotherapy. This might explain why participants who received cranial radiation ≥ 30 Gy alone were less informed than participants treated with platinum agents. This aligns with a previous record-based study in

which we found that CCS treated with cranial radiation ≥ 30 Gy were less likely to have received post-therapy hearing evaluations than CCS treated with platinum chemotherapy [29]. Participants reporting other late effects were more informed about the risk of hearing loss, suggesting that CCS with multiple late effects are generally more aware of treatment-related complications [30].

4.3. Hearing evaluations after end of treatment

A retrospective, record-based study examining audiological evaluations post-therapy in Switzerland found that 28 % of CCS at risk for hearing loss had not had any hearing evaluations after end of treatment [29]. This is comparable to the 32 % observed in our study. In our study, a further 30 % did not recall undergoing any hearing evaluations. While they might have had an initial test, CCS may not have had subsequent assessments when their hearing test result was normal as specified in older ASHA and Children's Oncology Group Long-Term Follow-Up Guidelines [28,31]. Given that initial hearing tests often occur during or soon after treatment, many may have forgotten about them or were not contacted for later hearing evaluations as currently recommended [1].

4.4. Degree of hearing loss and self-reported hearing loss

We previously reported that 36 % of CCS had clinically relevant hearing loss after platinum-based therapy according to the SIOP Boston ototoxicity scale [32]. This new study finds a higher prevalence (47 %) of clinically relevant hearing loss, likely because of different characteristics of the study population, which now is older and further from diagnosis and more recently represents the survivor cohort. Considering the newer study's low response rate, selection bias could have also played a role in the difference.

Almost half of our study participants with clinically relevant hearing loss did not report hearing problems as late effects in the questionnaire, suggesting they were not aware of them. The proportion of participants with hearing problems by SIOP Boston grade who did not self-report hearing loss was higher than that found in a previous study in which we compared questionnaire-reported hearing loss with audiometry results [33]. In that study, only 14 % of CCS who did not self-report hearing loss had hearing loss in the SIOP-Boston grade range from 1 to 4. In the current study, self-reported hearing loss was assessed using an open question about known late effects. We have potentially underestimated the proportion of participants who are aware about their hearing loss since some participants with hearing loss may not have listed it as a late effect.

4.5. Strengths and limitations

A strength of this study is the population-based sample with comprehensive cancer-related medical data provided by the Swiss ChCR. Combined with the questionnaire-based information and recent audiograms, our dataset allowed for a thorough analysis. Study limitations include the response rate of 25 % which, as noted above, potentially introduced selection bias. We sent two invitation reminders to CCS to enhance participation and increase the response rate. The low response rate may be due to the logistical efforts required as part of the HEAR-study setting, as CCS were not only asked to return a questionnaire but also had to make an appointment with a hearing aid shop themselves and visit the shop for a hearing test. Previous studies showed that open invitations to screening programs make participation less likely [34]. Invited study participants were also quite young (median age of 32 years), with some of them maybe not seeing the necessity to screen for hearing loss if they did not perceive any problems. Although analyses revealed some statistically significant differences between responders and nonresponders regarding cancer-related characteristics, differences were modest based upon effect sizes (see [Supplementary Table S5](#)).

4.6. Practice implications

How do we best manage survivorship to follow up treatment and address potential late effects? In addition to direct, clinical support of CCS and parents, electronic patient records continue to evolve and will improve the retention and support the acquisition of knowledge accessible by both providers and patients. A specific proposal for enhancing information access and retention for CCS is the Survivorship Passport, or SurPass [35]. This tool provides crucial details about a survivor's medical history and a tailored plan for follow-up to caregivers, and information for CCS that can inform their own decision-making; accessible online, it can be continually updated by new research findings. Highly secure yet accessible electronic records such as the SurPass can sustain awareness among caregivers and CCS wherever their journey through survivorship takes them. To facilitate ototoxic screening, alternative approaches such as the one proposed in the HEAR-study—where survivors visit hearing aid shops for audiological monitoring—may provide an accessible and practical option for screening. Integrating such a screening option into routine follow-up care could help ensure that more survivors get appropriate hearing screening.

5. Conclusion

A large proportion of CCS are not aware of the potential risk of hearing loss due to their treatment. Among those who are aware of this late effect, most have undergone hearing evaluations. From this we conclude that knowledge is key to timely interventions that can mitigate the effects of hearing loss. Caregivers, parents, and CCS should always have the latest information on late effects and follow-up care at hand to manage and protect auditory health throughout the lives of CCS—even those with decades intervening since treatment.

Abbreviations

ASHA	American Speech-Language-Hearing Association
CCS	Childhood cancer survivor
COG	Children's Oncology Group
CI	Confidence interval
IQR	Interquartile range
Gy	Gray

Funding

This work was financially supported by the Swiss Cancer League and Swiss Cancer Research (grant number HSR-4951-11-2019, KLS/KFS-5711-01-2022, and KFS-5302-02-2021). The CANSEARCH foundation, Kinderkrebs Schweiz Foundation, and Zoé4Life Foundation supported NW.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jörger Philippa: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Nigg Carina:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Formal analysis. **Zarković Maša:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis. **Sommer Grit:** Writing – review & editing. **Kompis Martin:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Michel Gisela:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Ansari Marc:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Waespe Nicolas:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Kuehni Claudia E.:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Nicolas Waespe reports a relationship with Swedish Orphan Biovitrum AB that includes advisory board membership, consulting, and travel reimbursement and a relationship with Novartis that includes advisory board membership. None of these relationships are in association with the current study.

Acknowledgements

We thank the study team of the Childhood Cancer Research Group, Institute of Social and Preventive Medicine, University of Bern, the Swiss Childhood Cancer Survivor Study, and the team of the Swiss Childhood Cancer Registry. We thank Christopher Ritter from the editorial service of the Institute of Social and Preventive Medicine at the University of Bern for the editorial suggestions. We thank all childhood cancer survivors participating in the study.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.pec.2025.108764](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2025.108764).

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Supplementary Tables & Figures: Awareness about and prevalence of hearing loss

Table of contents

Supplementary TABLE S1 Questions on late effects, hearing loss, information provision, awareness of hearing loss, and sociodemographic characteristics in from the HEAR-study (translated into English).....	2
Supplementary TABLE S2 Characteristics of participants by information status and factors associated with information status; results from univariable logistic regressions.....	3
Supplementary TABLE S3 Characteristics of participants by status of prior hearing evaluation; results from univariable logistic regressions.	4
Supplementary FIGURE SF1 Flowchart illustrating the HEAR-study population, depicting eligible survivors identified by the Swiss Childhood Cancer Registry.	5
Supplementary TABLE S4 Clinical risk factors for hearing loss in childhood cancer survivors who participated in the HEAR-study (N=105).	6
Supplementary TABLE S5 Demographic and clinical characteristics of study population, stratified by response status.	7
Supplementary TABLE S6 Calendar period of last completed hearing test (n=40).	8

Supplementary TABLE S1 Questions on late effects, hearing loss, information provision, awareness of hearing loss, and sociodemographic characteristics in from the HEAR-study (translated into English).

Variable	Question in questionnaire	Answer options
Presence of late effects	Are you suffering from a late effect of your previous cancer or its treatment?	Yes; no
Self-reported hearing loss	What late effects do you suffer from?	Open
General information received regarding follow-up care	Have you received written or verbal information from your pediatric oncologists regarding follow-up care?	Yes; no; don't know
Information status	Have you been informed that hearing impairment or hearing loss is possible after completion of therapy?	Yes; no; don't know
	Have you been advised to have your hearing checked after completing your therapy?	Yes; no; don't know
Regular visit of follow-up care	Do you still go to regular check-ups or follow-up care for your cancer?	Yes; no
Prior hearing evaluation	Has your hearing been checked after you have completed your cancer treatment?	Yes; no; don't know
Participant education	What is the highest level of education you have completed?	Obligatory; vocational training; high school; technical college; university
Education mother/father	What is your mother's/father's highest level of education?	Obligatory; vocational training; high school; technical college; university
Birthplace mother/father	In which country was your mother/father born?	Switzerland; don't know; other
Feeling of bad hearing	Do you sometimes have the feeling of not hearing well?	Yes, often; yes, sometimes; no
Hearing difficulties in noisy environments	Do you have problems following conversations in background noise, in a group, in a restaurant or with background music?	Yes; no

Supplementary TABLE S2 Characteristics of participants by information status and factors associated with information status; results from univariable logistic regressions.

	Informed/Advised yes N=46	Informed/Advised no or don't know know N=59	Univariable OR (95%-CI) N=105	p-value
	<i>n (%)</i>	<i>n (%)</i>		
Sex				
Female	24 (52)	33 (56)	1.0	
Male	22 (48)	26 (44)	1.2 (0.5-2.5)	0.70
Median age at study (IQR; Range)	29 (22-35; 18-43)	34 (25-45; 19-57)	0.9 (0.9-1.0)	<0.01
Median years since diagnosis (IQR; Range)	20 (17-26; 4-43)	27 (22-34; 7-44)	0.9 (0.9-1.0)	<0.01
Median age at diagnosis (IQR; Range)	10 (4-14; 0-19)	7 (3-13; 0-19)	1.0 (1.0-1.1)	0.19
Year of diagnosis (IQR; Range)	2002 (1996-2005; 1979-2018)	1995 (1987-2000; 1977-2014)	1.1 (1.0-1.2)	<0.01
≤1995	11 (24)	30 (51)	3.3 (1.4-7.7)	<0.01
>1995	35 (76)	29 (49)		
Language region				0.20
French	11 (24)	21 (36)	1.0	
German	35 (76)	38 (64)	1.8 (0.7-4.2)	
Participant education				
Primary or secondary education	29 (63)	33 (56)	1.0	
Tertiary education	17 (37)	26 (44)	0.7 (0.3-1.6)	0.46
Maternal education^a				
Primary or secondary education	29 (63)	47 (80)	1.0	
Tertiary education	16 (35)	11 (19)	2.4 (1.0-5.8)	0.06
Missing	1 (2)	1 (2)	NA	NA
Paternal education^a				
Primary or secondary education	28 (61)	44 (75)	1.0	
Tertiary education	17 (37)	15 (25)	1.8 (0.8-4.1)	0.18
Missing	1 (2)	0 (0)	NA	NA
Migration background^a				
No	29 (63)	35 (59)	1.0	
Yes	17 (37)	22 (37)	0.9 (0.4-2.1)	0.87
Missing	0 (0)	2 (3)	NA	NA
Late effects other than hearing loss				
No	9 (20)	24 (41)	1.0	
Yes	37 (80)	35 (59)	2.8 (1.2-6.9)	0.02
Self-reported hearing loss				
No	27 (59)	54 (92)	1.0	
Yes	19 (41)	5 (8)	7.6 (2.6-22.6)	<0.01
General information received on follow-up care				
No	24 (52)	43 (73)	1.0	
Yes	22 (48)	16 (27)	2.5 (1.1-5.6)	0.03
Regular visit of follow-up care				
No	20 (43)	38 (64)	1.0	
Yes	26 (57)	21 (36)	2.4 (1.1-5.2)	0.03
Treatment groups				
Cranial radiation ≥30 Gray only	3 (7)	20 (34)	1.0	
Platinum Chemotherapy only	32 (70)	31 (53)	6.9 (1.9-25.5)	<0.01
Both	11 (24)	6 (10)	12.2 (2.5-58.7)	<0.01
Missing	0	2 (3)	NA	NA

^a, People with missing maternal or paternal education, missing migration background and missing cisplatin were excluded from the univariable logistic regression.

Abbreviations: N, number OR, Odds Ratio. CI, Confidence Interval. IQR, Interquartile Range.

Supplementary TABLE S3 Characteristics of participants by status of prior hearing evaluation; results from univariable logistic regressions.

	Hearing evaluated yes N=40	Hearing evaluated no or didn't know N=65	Univariable OR (95%-CI) N=105	p-value
	<i>n (%)</i>	<i>n (%)</i>		
Sex				
Female	22 (55)	35 (54)	1.0	
Male	18 (45)	30 (46)	1.0 (0.4-2.1)	0.91
<i>Median age at study (IQR; Range)</i>	29 (24-35; 18-48)	34 (24-43; 19-57)	1.0 (0.9-1.0)	0.036
<i>Median years since diagnosis (IQR; Range)</i>	21 (17-26; 4-41)	26 (20-34; 4-44)	0.9 (0.9-1.0)	0.013
<i>Median age at diagnosis (IQR; Range)</i>	9 (3-14; 0-19)	8 (4-13; 0-19)	1.0 (1.0-1.1)	0.57
<i>Year of diagnosis (IQR; Range)</i>	2000 (1996-2005; 1981-2018)	1996 (1988-2002; 1977-2017)	1.1 (1.0-1.1)	0.01
≤1995	9 (23)	32 (49)	3.3 (1.4-8.1)	<0.01
>1995	31 (78)	33 (51)		
Language region				
French	11 (28)	21 (32)	1.0	
German	29 (73)	44 (68)	1.3 (0.5-3.0)	0.60
Participant education				
Primary or secondary education	27 (68)	35 (54)	1.0	
Tertiary education	13 (33)	30 (46)	0.6 (0.2-1.3)	0.17
Maternal education^a				
Primary or secondary education	24 (60)	52 (80)	1.0	
Tertiary education	15 (38)	12 (18)	2.8 (1.1-6.8)	0.03
Missing	1 (3)	1 (2)	NA	NA
Paternal education^a				
Primary or secondary education	25 (63)	47 (72)	1.0	
Tertiary education	14 (35)	18 (28)	1.5 (0.6-3.4)	0.38
Missing	1 (3)	0 (0)	NA	NA
Migration background^a				
No	24 (60)	40 (62)	1.0	
Yes	16 (40)	23 (35)	1.2 (0.5-2.6)	0.72
Missing	0 (0)	2 (3)	NA	NA
Late effects other than hearing loss				
No	7 (18)	26 (40)	1.0	
Yes	33 (83)	39 (60)	3.1 (1.2-8.2)	0.02
Self-reported hearing loss				
No	27 (68)	54 (83)	1.0	
Yes	13 (33)	11 (17)	2.4 (0.9-6.0)	0.07
General information received on follow-up care				
No	20 (50)	47 (72)	1.0	
Yes	20 (50)	18 (28)	2.6 (1.1-6.0)	0.02
Information/advice received on hearing loss and hearing screening				
No	7 (18)	52 (80)	1.0	
Yes	33 (83)	13 (20)	18.9 (6.8-52.1)	<0.01
Regular visit of follow-up care				
No	18 (45)	40 (62)	1.0	
Yes	22 (55)	25 (38)	2.0 (0.9-4.3)	0.10
Treatment groups^a				
Cranial radiation ≥30 Gray only	4 (10)	19 (29)	1.0	
Platinum Chemotherapy only	28 (70)	35 (54)	3.8 (1.2-12.5)	0.03
Both	8 (20)	9 (14)	4.2 (1.0-17.8)	0.05
Missing	0 (0)	2 (3)	NA	NA

^a, People with missing maternal or paternal education, missing migration background and missing platinum status were excluded from the univariable logistic regression.

Abbreviations: N, number OR, Odds Ratio. CI, Confidence Interval. IQR, Interquartile Range.

Supplementary FIGURE SF1 Flowchart illustrating the HEAR-study population, depicting eligible survivors identified by the Swiss Childhood Cancer Registry.

Abbreviations: ICCC-3, international classification of childhood cancer, edition 3. n, number.

Supplementary TABLE S4 Clinical risk factors for hearing loss in childhood cancer survivors who participated in the HEAR-study (N=105).

	Cranial radiation ≥30 Gray n (%)	No cranial radiation n (%)	Total n (%)
Cisplatin	4 (10)	38 (59)	42 (40)
Carboplatin	7 (17)	10 (16)	17 (16)
Cisplatin & Carboplatin	6 (15)	15 (23)	21 (20)
No platinum chemotherapy	23 (56)	0 (0)	23 (22)
Unknown	1 (2)	1 (2)	2 (2)
Total	41 (100)	64 (100)	105 (100)

Supplementary TABLE S5 Demographic and clinical characteristics of study population, stratified by response status.

	Total invited N=424	Completed questionnaire N=105	Did not respond to questionnaire N=319	p-value ^a	Cramér's V / Cohen's d ^b
	<i>n (%)</i>	<i>n (%)</i>	<i>n (%)</i>		
Sex				0.08	0.08
Female	199 (47)	57 (54)	142 (45)		
Male	225 (53)	48 (46)	177 (55)		
Age at study, years (Median, IQR)	29 (23-37)	32 (24-37)	29 (22-36)	0.03	0.24
18-25	148 (35)	33 (31)	115 (36)		
26-34	141 (33)	31 (30)	110 (34)		
35-57	135 (32)	41 (39)	94 (29)		
Year of diagnosis (Median, range)	1999 (1977-2019)	1998 (1977-2018)	2000 (1978-2019)	0.02	0.25
1977-1995	147 (35)	33 (31)	114 (36)		
1996-2003	153 (36)	39 (37)	114 (36)		
2004-2019	124 (29)	33 (31)	91 (29)		
Time since diagnosis, years (Median, IQR)	22 (16-30)	23 (19-32)	21 (16-29)	0.03	0.25
3-18	143 (34)	25 (24)	118 (37)		
19-26	144 (34)	40 (38)	104 (33)		
27-44	137 (32)	40 (38)	97 (30)		
Age at cancer diagnosis, years (Median, IQR)	9 (3.5-13)	8 (4-13)	9 (3-13)	0.87	0.02
≤5	147 (35)	33 (31)	114 (36)		
6-12	153 (36)	39 (37)	114 (36)		
13-20	124 (29)	33 (31)	91 (29)		
Diagnostic group of primary neoplasm (ICCC-3)				0.01	0.23
Leukemias (I)	8 (2)	0 (0)	8 (3)		
Lymphomas (II)	17 (4)	7 (7)	10 (3)		
CNS (III)	111 (26)	23 (22)	88 (28)		
Neuroblastoma (IV)	42 (10)	13 (12)	29 (9)		
Retinoblastoma (V)	15 (4)	3 (3)	12 (4)		
Renal tumors (VI)	30 (7)	2 (2)	28 (9)		
Hepatic tumors (VII)	11 (3)	4 (4)	7 (2)		
Malignant bone tumors (VIII)	71 (17)	24 (23)	47 (15)		
Soft tissue (IX)	67 (16)	22 (21)	45 (14)		
Germ cell tumors (X)	49 (12)	7 (7)	42 (13)		
Other (XI)	3 (1)	0 (0)	3 (1)		
Platinum Chemotherapy				0.50	0.10
No platinum chemotherapy	91 (21)	23 (22)	68 (21)		
Cisplatin	148 (35)	42 (40)	106 (33)		
Carboplatin	92 (22)	17 (16)	75 (24)		
Cisplatin & Carboplatin	78 (18)	21 (20)	57 (18)		
Unknown	15 (4)	2 (2)	13 (4)		
Cranial radiation				0.57	0.07
No cranial radiation	253 (60)	64 (61)	189 (59)		
<30 Gray	3 (1)	0 (0)	3 (1)		
≥30 Gray	165 (39)	41 (39)	124 (39)		
Unknown	3 (1)	0 (0)	3 (1)		

Abbreviations: n, number. IQR, Interquartile Range. ICCC-3, international classification of childhood cancer, edition 3. CNS, central nervous system.

^a p-values calculated from chi-square statistics for categorical variables and two-sided t-test for continuous variables, comparing responders to non-responders.

^b Effect sizes were calculated using Cramér's V for categorical and Cohen's d for continuous variables.

Supplementary TABLE S6 Calendar period of last completed hearing test (n=40).

Year	Participants N=40 (n, (%))
<2020	12 (30)
2020-2022	13 (33)
Do not remember	15 (38)

Abbreviations: n, number.